

HyDelta 3

WP5e – Technology & safety in the hydrogen network – Gas stations

WP5e.2 – Potential hardware fixes for hydrogen gas station ventilation

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Document summary

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Summary

In the Netherlands, there are approximately 60,000 gas pressure regulating stations. Each station is placed in a gas cabinet that shields the technical installation from the public environment. Ventilation is a mitigating measure for an operational gas leak in a gas pressure regulating station. In the Netherlands, the ventilation requirements for gas pressure regulating stations for natural gas are described in the NEN1059. Table 3 in this normative standard describes the minimum ventilation requirements for gas cabinet of a gas pressure regulating stations. During HyDelta 1.0 and 2.0, [1, 2], a range of experiments were carried out to gain insight into the ventilation properties of the gas cabinets in the case of hydrogen distribution. Representative gas cabinets used by the Dutch gas network operators were selected, whereby a 1/2m³ cabinet and a 4m³ cabinet station were tested at various leak rates for both natural gas and hydrogen. The selected leak rates partly overlap in size between the different HyDelta programs. During these studies, it was demonstrated that improving the ventilation concept is desirable when using hydrogen.

After consultation with the Expert Assessment Group, it was decided to use the 1/2m³ gas cabinet again, which was also tested in previous HyDelta projects, mainly because these cabinets are used most in existing gas distribution networks. This also offers the advantage that this cabinet can be easily adapted in terms of ventilation. In addition, measurements have already taken place with this cabinet in its original state (without adjustments). This housing has a standard ventilation of 2% of the floor area (in case of top ventilation) in accordance with NEN1059.

During HyDelta 1.0 and 2.0 experiments, it was established that there is a difference in leakage rate for an incident or an operational leakage. An incident leakage is a leak as a result of the failure of components and an operational leak is a leak that can be expected during normal use, among other things as a result of applied coupling techniques. The ventilation of a housing must be able to adequately ventilate an operational leakage, which will be practically impossible in the event of an incident. Based on research commissioned by the Dutch normative committee "gas pressure regulating stations" it was established that an operational leak corresponds in size to 40 l/h natural gas [3, 4] for the Netherlands. This is an important starting point for follow-up studies into ventilation and ventilation capabilities of cabinets.

For hydrogen, it is of interest to know to what extent the current ventilation is sufficient to ventilate an operational leak. Hydrogen behaves differently than natural gas and has different physical and chemical properties, which means that a leak may have different consequences. During HyDelta 2.0, it was determined that with the same upstream pressure and leak opening, a leak rate of 125 l/h of hydrogen is present (whereas a leak rate of 40 l/h was determined for natural gas).

Gas concentration measurements at the above-mentioned leak rates lead to values of around 3 vol% hydrogen in a 1/2m³ cabinet and to around 1 vol% natural gas. The gas concentration with hydrogen is therefore closer to the lower flammability limit. In HyDelta 3.0, it was examined how the current ventilation of a gas pressure regulating station can be updated to be able to comply with hydrogen situations in the future, depending on which operational leak is assumed.

Here, the ventilation in a 1/2m³ cabinet was adjusted by placing multiple ventilation grilles. With these adjustments and an operational leak of 40 l/h natural gas and 125 l/h hydrogen respectively, concentration measurements were performed. This leads to lower gas concentrations in the gas cabinet. Larger leak rates were also examined to test how robust the solution of adjusting the ventilation really is.

The current gas pressure regulation stations are built based on the NEN1059 and this standard describes that equipment placed inside a gas cabinet must comply with the area classification according to ATEX regulations. The normative standard also states which ventilation must be applied to the different types of gas cabinets. This makes the gas pressure regulating stations and the housings of the gas pressure regulating stations suitable for use with natural gas and therefore adjustments to the ventilation are not necessary.

This research program with hydrogen has shown that the ventilation capabilities of an existing cabinet can be improved by increasing the ventilation openings area. This results in a lower equilibrium concentration for the same leakage, which can be successfully applied for an application with hydrogen. This is also the reason why increasing ventilation is mentioned in this report as a “quick win”.

Glossary

Housing	installation space for a gas pressure regulation and/or measuring system
Gas pressure regulator - and measuring station	complete set of gas pressure regulation and/or measuring installation, housing, location and associated (electrical) facilities, limited by and including the isolation valves.
cupboard	enclosure with a volume (V_r) less than or equal to 0.5 m^3 Note 1 to the term: The cabinet is considered inaccessible by definition .
Cabinet station	enclosure with a volume (V_r) greater than 0.5 m^3 and less than 15 m^3 Note 1 to the entry: A cabinet station may or may not be accessible .
Mini cabinet	enclosure with a volume (V_r) less than or equal to 0.1 m^3 Note 1 to the term: The cabinet is considered inaccessible by definition .
District station (DS)	gas pressure regulation and measuring station for gas pressure regulation of gas from high-pressure distribution network to a low-pressure distribution network.
Gas pressure regulation system (PRS)	facility, containing all components, including inlet and outlet pipes up to and including the isolation valves, which together function as gas pressure regulation and/or pressure protection.
High pressure delivery station (HAS)	a gas pressure regulation and/or measuring station, installed externally , of category A7, A8 or A9 according to NEN-1059 (2019).
m^3 under normal conditions (m^3_n)	quantity of gas which, in the dry state and at a pressure of $101\,325 \text{ Pa}$ and a temperature of 273.15 K ($0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$), has a volume of 1 m^3 .
Pressure control system	system that ensures that the pressure in the exhaust line is maintained within the required limits.
Top ventilation / bottom ventilation / cross ventilation	When applying top ventilation, ventilation openings are made at the top of a housing, allowing natural ventilation to take place. The contents of the housing can be refreshed in this way. In the case of bottom ventilation, ventilation openings are made at the bottom of the housing. In the case of cross ventilation, ventilation openings are made at both the top and the bottom.
Ventilation factor (V_v)	The number of times the air in a room is refreshed.
Ventilation capacity	A unit that indicates the ratio between the air exchange in a space and the volume of that space at the considered leakage rate of the hazard source present in the space.
Druk	A force per unit area, in which the SI system speaks of Pa or bar. Relative pressure is always a measured value compared to a reference value, usually compared to the air pressure. The relative pressure can be higher or lower than that reference value, respectively overpressure and underpressure. To indicate the difference, the letter g (gauge) or a (absolute) is placed after the unit, so that for example 2 bara corresponds to 1 barg.

LFL	LFL refers to the lower flammability limit. Below the lower flammability limit, there is insufficient fuel to sustain a combustion reaction. For hydrogen, the LFL is 4 vol% hydrogen in air, for natural gas the LFL is 5 vol% natural gas in air.
UFL	UFL refers to the upper flammability limit. Above the upper flammability limit, there is insufficient oxygen to sustain a combustion reaction. For hydrogen, the UFL is 75 vol% hydrogen in air, for natural gas, the UFL is 15 vol% natural gas in air.
Median	The median is the middle value of a group of numbers ranked by size. It is the number that lies exactly in the middle so that 50% of the ranked numbers are above 50% and 50% are below the median.
Enclosures	Small type: housings for HAS installations are usually situated with a volume $\leq 0.25 \text{ m}^3$. Medium type: housings for DS/AS stations are often situated with a volume $\leq 0.5 \text{ m}^3$. Large type housings for larger DS/OS stations are often situated with a volume $\leq 4 \text{ m}^3$.
Schoepen grille	Louvre grilles ensure continuous air renewal and air extraction. The blades prevent rain from entering. A louvre grille is therefore suitable for outside, but can also be used inside. The blades mean that the effective ventilation surface is smaller than the openness of the ventilation openings. Grilles should be placed vertically to prevent rain from entering.
EAG	Expert Assessment Group; experts from the Dutch gas network operators

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Increasing ventilation with ventilation grilles leads to a lower equilibrium concentration and is a relatively simple quick win

The ventilation requirements of gas pressure regulating stations in the Netherlands are dictated by NEN1059. Table 3 of this normative standard describes the minimum ventilation surface required for ventilating the cabinet of a gas pressure regulating station. During HyDelta 1.0 and 2.0 [1] [2], various experiments were carried out to gain insight into the required ventilation for hydrogen. Representative cabinets for the Netherlands were used for this, with a 1/2m³ cabinet and a 4m³ cabinet station being tested for both natural gas and hydrogen. During these studies, it was demonstrated that when using hydrogen, improving the ventilation concept is required. This is mainly due to the difference in physical properties between natural gas and hydrogen.

In HyDelta 3.0 the question was formulated which simple adjustments (with regard to ventilation) can be made to improve the ventilation of an (existing) cabinet. By placing four elongated grilles in the housing for the HyDelta tests, the ventilation is increased from 2% to almost 14%. Two grilles are placed at the front, two at the back. By placing these ventilation grilles, experiments have shown that the ventilation can be improved for both natural gas and hydrogen leaks.

The photo below shows how the elongated ventilation grilles are fitted. In this project, blade grilles were chosen to prevent water ingress as much as possible.

Figure 1. Modified cabinet with 4 louvre grilles, on the right a detail of one of the louvre grilles

Previous research has established that there is a clear difference between an operational leak and an incident. The ventilation of a housing must be able to adequately ventilate an operational leak, which is practically impossible in the event of an incident. Based on research commissioned by the Dutch standards committee, it has been established that an operational leak is equivalent in size to 40 l/h of natural gas [4]. During HyDelta 2.0, it was also determined that a leak at the same pressure and leak size opening results in a leak flow rate of 125 l/h (where a leak rate of 40 l/h was established for natural gas).

As previously established, all measured equilibrium concentrations for the housing are already below the lower flammability limit without modifications, however, by increasing the ventilation, by adding ventilation grilles, a lower equilibrium concentration can be achieved. This results in less accumulation of gas in a housing in the event of an operational leak, thereby reducing the potential risk.

When an operational leakage of 40 l/h natural gas and 125 l/h hydrogen respectively is simulated in the housing with modified ventilation, lower equilibrium concentrations are achieved in the housing than during HyDelta 2.0. The graph below compares the results of HyDelta 2.0 (the standard ventilation in this housing, 2% top ventilation) and the improved ventilation (addition of four ventilation grilles, total 14% ventilation).

Figure 2. Concentration (vol%) for natural gas and hydrogen in a $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ cabinet during HyDelta 2.0 and HyDelta 3.0

The graph shows that a lower average equilibrium concentration is measured for both natural gas and hydrogen. This is the case both in the housing and at the ventilation openings. In the NEN1059 (appendix E3.3), it is stated that in order to determine a non-hazardous area (NGG), the gas concentration must be at a maximum of 80% of the lower flammability limit for a non-accessible cabinet. In HyDelta 2.0, it can be seen that this value is almost achieved for hydrogen with a leakage of 125 l/h.

Adding extra ventilation is therefore a quick win for lowering the equilibrium concentration in an operational leak. When the measurements are studied more closely, the following can be concluded:

Measurement results $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ cabinet (HyDelta 2.0) – standard, without additional measures

- In the event of a leak of 40 l/h of natural gas, the maximum gas concentration in a $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ cabinet is approximately 1 vol%, a mixture with a lower concentration than the lower flammability limit¹.
- In a comparable leak for hydrogen (125 l/h), the concentration rises to 2.7 vol%, which is also less than the lower flammability limit. Similar concentrations are measured directly at the ventilation openings, with 3.2 vol% as a local, time-dependent peak. At half a meter from the housing, the concentration is in all cases well below the flammability limit.

Measurement results $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ cabinet (HyDelta 3.0) – with additional ventilation openings

- In the event of a leak of 40 l/h of natural gas, the maximum gas concentration in a $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ cabinet is less than 0.5 vol%, a mixture below the lower flammability limit¹.
- In a comparable leak for hydrogen (125 l/h), the concentration rises to 1.4 vol%, which is also below the lower flammability limit. Much lower concentrations are measured directly at the ventilation openings, around 0.2 vol%. At half a meter from the housing, the concentration is in all cases well below the flammability limit.

All measured equilibrium concentrations for the housing without modifications are already below the lower flammability limit. Only by increasing the ventilation by adding ventilation grilles can a lower

¹With definition as added in glossary

equilibrium concentration be achieved, which results in less accumulation of gas in a housing in the event of an operational leak.

When a simplified calculation is made for the effectiveness of the ventilation, the following can be stated. A leakage of 40 l/h leads to a total leakage volume of 6.7 liters of natural gas in 10 minutes (the duration of the experiment) $(10 \text{ [min]}/60 \text{ [min]} \times 40 \text{ [l/h]})$.

This amount of natural gas is released in a cabinet of $\frac{1}{2} \text{ m}^3$. This housing also contains the gas pressure regulation station itself, which takes up space (approximately 15% of the total volume). This reduces the volume available for air (with a little natural gas from the leak) to $0.425 \text{ m}^3 ((100 \text{ [%]} - 15 \text{ [%]}) \times 0.5 \text{ (m}^3))$.

If a comparison is made between the theoretical maximum gas concentration (all gas remains trapped in the housing) and the measured average gas concentration based on HyDelta 2.0 and HyDelta 3.0 results, the following table can be compiled;

Table 1. The effectiveness of ventilation is influenced by the availability of ventilation

Test program	With/without extra ventilation	Medium	Leakage rate [l/h]	Theoretical maximum concentration [vol%]	Measured average concentration [vol%]	Ventilation effectiveness [%]
HyDelta 3.0	With	Natural gas	40	1.57	0.20	87.3%
HyDelta 2.0	Without	Natural gas	40	1.57	0.60	63.7%
HyDelta 3.0	With	Hydrogen	125	4.90	0.70	85.7%
HyDelta 2.0	Without	Hydrogen	125	4.90	2,15	56.1%

For both natural gas and hydrogen, this simplified calculation shows that by increasing the available ventilation surface area, the ventilation characteristics for a $\frac{1}{2} \text{ m}^3$ housing improve for both natural gas and hydrogen.

Different ventilation concepts lead to relatively small differences in effectiveness

The previous paragraph shows that increasing the ventilation area by adding ventilation grilles can improve the ventilation capabilities for a gas pressure regulation station housing. Ventilation can be applied in various ways (read: concepts). In the case of the $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ cabinet (that is the key cabinet for this research), four elongated blade grilles were installed. Two grilles at approximately 10 cm below the roof edge and two grilles at approximately 10 cm above the cast iron base on either side of the housing, which is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the ventilation grilles in the $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ housing (front). At the rear of the housing, the ventilation grilles are placed in an identical manner.

By varying the number of open grilles, different ventilation concepts can be tested, whereby a distinction is made between:

- **Top ventilation;** two additional grilles at the top (total ventilation area \sim 8%).
- **Cross ventilation;** two additional grilles, but placed so that the air flow runs diagonally. This was tested in the trial by placing a grille at the front at the top and at the back at the bottom (total ventilation area \sim 8%).
- **Maximum ventilation ;** four additional grilles (total ventilation area \sim 14%).

In conclusion, it can be stated that the mutual differences in the measured gas concentration (due to the ventilation behaviour) are small for both natural gas and hydrogen. In general, adding extra ventilation results in a lower equilibrium concentration.

Test procedure

A standardized testing method has been set up for testing the various ventilation concepts according to a test procedure. An experiment is started with a leak of 40 l/h natural gas (respectively 125 l/h hydrogen) whereby the gas concentration in and around the housing is measured until it stabilizes. The leak rate is then doubled and measured again until the measured gas concentrations stabilize. In total, the leak rate is doubled four times. This results in the following test matrix whereby a total of five leak rates are tested with three ventilation concepts;

Table 2 Leakage rates for natural gas and hydrogen.

	Leak rate 1	Leak rate 2	Leak rate 3	Leak rate 4	Leak rate 5
Natural gas (m ³ _n /h) *	0.04	0.08	0.16	0.32	0.64
Natural gas (l/h) *	40	80	160	320	640
Natural gas (g/s) *	0.009	0.019	0.037	0.074	0.148
Hydrogen (m ³ _n /h) *	0.125	0.250	0.500	1.0	2.0
Hydrogen (l/h) *	125	250	500	1000	2000
Hydrogen (g/s) *	0.003	0.006	0.012	0.25	0.50

*) Rounding off numbers and significant figures reserved

When all bandwidths of the measured natural gas concentrations are plotted for maximum ventilation, top ventilation and cross ventilation, the picture shown in Figure 4. Appendix I and II discusses the test setup and the measuring equipment used in more detail.

Results

In order to make the results visually clear and recognizable, it was decided to express the various measurements in the graph below in an average measured gas concentration with a bandwidth as a measure for the fluctuations in measured values. This simplification makes it easier to obtain a comparison for the various ventilation concepts.

Figure 4. Average gas concentration (vol%) at different leakage rates of natural gas in a 1/2 m³ cabinet

When Figure 4 is considered, the following preliminary conclusions could be drawn for the case of natural gas:

1. All types of ventilation show an upward trend with an increase in leakage rate;
2. At maximum ventilation, stabilization of average concentration above 0.16 m³(n)/h occurs. It is also noticeable that the bandwidth is smaller for maximum ventilation, which indicates less accumulation in the housing;
3. For both top ventilation and cross ventilation, the upward trend is slightly steeper than for maximum ventilation, considering the average concentration.

For maximum ventilation, it can also be determined that for leaks up to $0.64 \text{ m}^3(\text{n})/\text{h}$ natural gas, all average values remain below the lower flammability limit. The performance of maximum ventilation is better than top- and cross ventilation across the board, which results in lower average concentrations at the same leak rate. Appendix IV contains all graphs for maximum ventilation, top ventilation and cross ventilation. In general, it can be stated that for leaks up to $0.32 \text{ m}^3(\text{n})/\text{h}$ natural gas, the average gas concentration remains below the lower flammability limit.

When the average measured gas concentrations are plotted for hydrogen with the different ventilation concepts in the same way as for natural gas, the following picture emerges;

Figure 5. Average gas concentration (vol%) at different hydrogen leakage rates in a $\frac{1}{2} \text{ m}^3$ cabinet

When Figure 5 is considered, the following preliminary conclusions could be drawn for the case of hydrogen:

1. All types of ventilation show an upward trend with an increase in leakage rate; Average concentrations are higher compared to natural gas;
2. At maximum ventilation, the average concentration does not stabilize; with increasing leakage rate, the measured gas concentration also increases;
3. For both top ventilation and cross ventilation an upward trend can be seen which is slightly steeper than for maximum ventilation. This indicates more accumulation for these ventilation concepts.

For maximum ventilation, it can also be seen from the graph that for leaks up to $0.5 \text{ m}^3(\text{n})/\text{h}$ hydrogen, all average values remain below the lower flammability limit. The performance of maximum ventilation is slightly better for all leaks than top and cross ventilation, which leads to lower average concentrations at the same leak rate. Appendix IV contains all graphs for maximum ventilation, top ventilation and cross ventilation. In general it can be stated that for leaks up to $0.5 \text{ m}^3(\text{n})/\text{h}$ hydrogen the gas concentration remains below the lower flammability limit.

In conclusion, it can be stated that it is surprising that the mutual differences in ventilation behaviour are small for both natural gas and hydrogen. However, adding extra ventilation does result in a lower equilibrium concentration in this housing and at the ventilation openings. The consideration to use one of the concepts mainly depends on the type of housing and the intended safety margin.

Larger ventilation openings can vent larger leaks

By installing additional ventilation grilles in the $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ housing, the influence on the measured gas concentrations at different leak rates was examined. By doubling the leakage in steps from 40 l/h natural gas (respectively 125 l/h hydrogen), the stabilization of the gas concentration in and around the housing is measured. In total, the leakage rate has been doubled four times for both natural gas and hydrogen.

It can be stated that, independent of the type of ventilation, the robustness of the ventilation capabilities increases for both natural gas and hydrogen leaks. Adding ventilation grilles to a $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ housing leads to improved ventilation behaviour and can adequately ventilate larger leaks. However, the effectiveness does have a maximum where up to a certain point, adding more ventilation does not lead to a lower equilibrium concentration.

When the average measured gas concentrations for natural gas and hydrogen are plotted for different leak rates, the graphs below are obtained. In these graphs, the lower flammability limit for natural gas (5 vol% LFL) and hydrogen (4 vol% LFL) is also plotted.

Figure 6. Average gas concentration (vol%) at different leakage rates of natural gas in a $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ cabinet

Figure 7. Average gas concentration (vol%) at different hydrogen leakage rates in a $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ cabinet

Regardless of the type of ventilation (maximum ventilation, top ventilation or cross ventilation), the equilibrium concentration is lower than measured with the standard ventilation as described in Figure 2.

For natural gas leaks, a leak of up to 0.32 m³(n)/h can still be adequately ventilated away with any type of ventilation, based on the chosen increase in ventilation in these tests for this specific type of housing ($\frac{1}{2}$ m³ cabinet).

With hydrogen, it is particularly noticeable that the bandwidth around the average gas concentration is more influenced by the type of ventilation. For hydrogen leaks, a leak of up to 0.25 m³(n)/h can still be adequately removed with any ventilation concept, based on the chosen increase in ventilation in these tests for this specific type of housing.

When only the average measured gas concentrations (the crosses in the bar charts) are considered, the results are more positive. In that case, a natural gas leak of up to 0.64 m³(n)/h remains below the lower flammability limit, while this is the case for a hydrogen leak of up to 1.0 m³(n)/h.

When calculating the effectiveness of ventilation in the same way (as was done previously for an operational leak rate of 40 l/h natural gas and equivalent 125 l/h hydrogen), the effectiveness of ventilation can be determined for all tested leak rates. This is visualized in the graph below for the tests with maximum ventilation, where the leak rate has been converted to energy content (calorific value) so that natural gas and hydrogen can be better compared with each other;

Figure 8. Effectiveness of ventilation for different leakage rates in a ½ m³ cabinet

The possibility of ventilation depends on the availability of ventilation, but also on the size of the leak flow. This has also been demonstrated in HyDelta 2.0 by comparing measurement results and mathematical equations [2]. However, this does not mean that the gas concentration will always decrease further by adding more ventilation. Figure 8 mainly shows that adding more ventilation does not lead to an improvement in the effectiveness for all leaks and that there is asymptotic behaviour in the effectiveness.

In addition, with a larger leak the percentage effectiveness is better despite the fact that the absolute measured gas concentration is higher. With a smaller leak, the percentage effectiveness even drops

somewhat. The turbulence, resulting from the larger leakage is an important driving force in the ventilation behaviour because it contributes to the mixing of the gas (from the leakage) with the air in the housing. While maintaining momentum and continuity of mass, a larger leak ensures its own dilution and the supply of fresh air. The total available surface of the ventilation openings as well as their position determine how significant this contribution is. This effect is more pronounced for natural gas than for hydrogen because the larger density difference with air in the case of hydrogen causes a rapid decrease in the conservation of momentum.

The grey part of the line for natural gas is an extrapolation based on all measurements for 40 l/h natural gas. If only the average value of this measurement is taken, it does not follow the trend line and the effectiveness is higher (around 87%). This trend break cannot be explained properly with the measurements.

The same behaviour can also be observed for cross-ventilation and top ventilation, although the effectiveness here is logically slightly lower due to the difference in available ventilation surface. As a result, the scalability of the effectiveness of ventilation results in a trend which is not so clear.

Adding ventilation grilles to a $\frac{1}{2}\text{m}^3$ housing improves the ventilation behaviour and can adequately ventilate larger leaks. A multiple of an operational leak (40 l/h natural gas, respectively 125 l/h hydrogen) can be ventilated in this way without exceeding the lower flammability limit. However, the effectiveness does have a maximum, where adding more ventilation does not lead to a lower equilibrium concentration.

The degree of stratification is greater with hydrogen than with natural gas

For both natural gas and hydrogen, it has been shown that small differences exist for the $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ cabinet when the same leakage flow rate is compared in a housing with different ventilation concepts.

When specifically zooming in on the gas concentration build-up in the housing as a result of the leak, interesting conclusions can also be drawn. The figure below plots the average gas concentration at three points in the housing; housing-middle (KM), housing-high (KH) and housing-high-ventilation (KHV). The difference in concentration between KM, KH and KHV is a measure of how well the gas can escape via the ventilation grilles. Where for natural gas the differences between KM (at the level of the gas leak), KH (10 cm under the roof) and KHV (at the level of the ventilation slot in the roof edge) are clearly present, where the natural gas concentration is immediately lower than in the middle of the housing (KM), this is significantly less for hydrogen. For hydrogen, the mutual differences between KH and KHV are small, which indicates the formation of a blanket with a uniform concentration.

Figure 9. Average gas concentration (vol%) at different leakage rates of natural gas (left) and hydrogen (right) in a $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ cabinet

For natural gas, it can also be seen that the gas concentration under the roof increases slightly again because the gas has to leave the housing via the ventilation slot in the roof structure.

The limiting effects of a roof construction as used in the tested $\frac{1}{2}$ m³ housing were also seen in the previous HyDelta 2.0 study. During HyDelta 2.0, in addition to experiments, simulations were also performed with finite element methods (CFD) for natural gas (0.45 and 3.0 m³(n)/h) and hydrogen (0.6 and 6.0 m³(n)/h). With a much smaller ventilation surface of only 2% in the roof edge of the housing, blanket formation (stratification) was observed in all cases. This creates a blanket with a uniform concentration that is only diluted to a limited extent by the supply of air from outside the housing. This effect was the smallest for the simulations with 0.6 m³(n)/h.

The ventilation of housings for natural gas pressure regulating stations does not need to be adjusted

As for natural gas, all housings of current gas pressure regulating stations must comply with ATEX regulations. The starting point here has always been that the lower flammability limit may not be exceeded in the event of a regular leak.

The standard for gas pressure regulating stations, NEN1059: 2019, currently states:

According to ATEX, a gas pressure regulation system is a secondary grade of release. The system must be technically gas-tight when commissioned and during operation. The installation space of the gas pressure regulation system is classified as ATEX zone 1, or as ATEX zone 2 if it can be demonstrated that the ventilation rate of the installation space is greater than 5 h^{-1} (classification according to NEN-EN-IEC 60079-10).

In the housing of a gas pressure regulating station, a zone 2 is assigned according to the NPR7910, section 9.4, with sufficient ventilation (more than 5x per hour). This means that all equipment placed in this zone must be suitable to use in this zone, even when it is possible that on occasions (according to the definition of a secondary grade of release), a flammable mixture is present in the housing. This also means that it may occasionally be possible for a flammable mixture to exist in the housing according to the definition of a secondary hazard source. If it would be preferable to alleviate the regime (for example from a zone 2 classification to a NGG (non-hazardous area) classification), the ventilation must be improved.

The current gas pressure regulating stations are built based on the NEN1059. The standard prescribes the minimum ventilation requirement as a percentage of the floor area for various types of housings. The standard also describes the boundary conditions for zoning the housing of a gas pressure regulating station. This makes the gas pressure regulating stations and the housings of the gas pressure regulating stations suitable for use with natural gas and therefore adjustments to the ventilation are not necessary.

The basis for this research on ventilation (and also previous research within HyDelta) is focused on the use of hydrogen and to what extent the current ventilation of a housing is sufficient for hydrogen. During these studies, tests were performed with commonly used housings by Dutch grid operators. The observations are that the results for natural gas and hydrogen differ due to the difference in physical properties such as density and flammability limits. The results of the tests with natural gas and hydrogen show different concentration gradients due to the difference in physical properties such as density and flammability limits.

The research for natural gas confirms that the current requirements are sufficient, and that there is no reason for additional measures. Due to the different physical properties, this is not always the case with hydrogen and extra attention is necessary. Adding additional ventilation for a gas pressure regulating station on hydrogen is a quick win.

Adding ventilation effectively reduces the effect of stratification for natural gas compared to hydrogen. The buoyancy of hydrogen in the unmodified cabinet will cause a (more or less) stagnant layer in the upper part of the housing, which contributes to stratification. Adding ventilation effectively reduces the stratification for a hydrogen leakage.

Conclusions and recommendations

During HyDelta 1.0 and 2.0, [1, 2], a range of experiments were carried out to gain insight into the ventilation properties of the gas cabinets in the case of hydrogen distribution. Representative gas cabinets used by the Dutch gas network operators were selected, whereby a 1/2m³ cabinet and a 4m³ cabinet station were tested at various leak rates for both natural gas and hydrogen. During these previous studies, it was demonstrated that improving the ventilation concept is desirable when using hydrogen. This is mainly due to the difference in physical properties between natural gas and hydrogen. In addition, the ventilation openings used in a housing as currently applied influences the effectiveness of the ventilation.

Ventilating a gas cabinet is a mitigating measure to reduce the potential effects of a gas leakage. This study looked into simple adjustments to improve the ventilation capabilities of an existing housing. By increasing the effective ventilation surface area, various ventilation concepts were tested for a 1/2m³ cabinet since this configuration is frequently used by network operators in their existing gas distribution networks.

Based on this research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Increasing ventilation capabilities with the installation of ventilation grilles lead to a lower equilibrium concentration in the cabinet and is a relatively simple quick win;
- Different ventilation concepts lead to relatively small differences in effectiveness;
- Larger ventilation openings can ventilate larger leaks in view of the 80% LFL limit according to the normative standard (for non-accessible spaces like a small cabinet) involving a NGG (where work can take place). Here, each leak rate is limited by the percentage of ventilation that is added in the form of additional ventilation grilles;
- The degree of stratification is greater with hydrogen than with natural gas;
- There are limits to the effectiveness of ventilation as a mitigating measure for a leakage. Adding extra ventilation surface area cannot prevent large leaks from leading to a high(er) equilibrium concentration.
- The current gas pressure regulation stations are built in accordance with the Dutch normative standard, the NEN1059. This normative standard prescribes the minimum ventilation requirements as a percentage of the floor area for various types of gas cabinets. The standard also describes the boundary conditions for the area classification according to ATEX regulations. This makes the gas pressure regulating stations and the housings of the gas pressure regulating stations suitable for use with natural gas and therefore adjustments to the ventilation are not necessary.

For future (pilot) projects with a hydrogen gas pressure regulation station, it is recommended to increase the effective ventilation surface by means of additional ventilation grilles. One type of 1/2m³ housing and the range of leakage rates in this study were chosen as a starting point. The consideration to use one of the concepts mainly depends on the type of housing and the intended safety margin.

In addition, it is advisable to look at the type of ventilation grilles that are used. In this study, louvre grilles were used, but each type of grille has specific characteristics that influence the effectiveness of the ventilation. Denser grilles (for example, Y-grilles that make it more difficult to throw objects in) are constructed differently, resulting in higher hydraulic resistance that may worsen the ventilation. When adapting a housing, the integrity of the housing should also be considered. The strength and torsional stiffness will decrease when grilles are placed in the side walls of the housing. Reinforcements may therefore have to be applied. This was not part of the current study, but should be included.

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Appendix I – Test setup and chosen method

As mentioned before, this research can best be seen as a further development of HyDelta 1.0 and 2.0. The same test setup was used for this, which is why the description was partly taken from the report of HyDelta 1.0 and 2.0.

The test setup consists of:

- Gas cylinders with hydrogen, natural gas and nitrogen
- A gas pressure regulator and a mass flow controller (MFC).
- A standard cabinet ($1/2 \text{ m}^3$) with only top ventilation ($\sim 2\%$), supplied by Enexis. This cabinet has been modified with four ventilation grilles, type louvre grilles.
- A pipe used to introduce a leak with an outflow opening of 0.25 and 0.025 mm^2 into the station. The leak is positioned in the middle of the cabinet. It is also possible to connect a needle valve to the outflow opening.

Figure 10. Schematic representation of test setup

Measuring points and measuring equipment

The natural gas or hydrogen concentration is measured at the following points:

- In the cabinet at 4 points (bottom, middle and 2x above). The measuring point "middle" (2), is 10 cm away from the outlet opening. The measuring points "bottom" (1) and "above" (3) are directly below and above the measuring point "middle", at 5 cm distance from ground level or the top of the cabinet (for the $1/2\text{m}^3$ cabinet). Schematically, the arrangement of the measuring points looks like this;

Figure 11 Setup of the measuring points in the test setup ($1/2\text{m}^3$ cabinet), side view (left) and top view (right)

- Directly outside the case at 8 points (points 5 to 12) on the long side of the case near the ventilation openings, approximately 5 cm from the extreme left/right side. For this purpose, the Riken Keiki sensors used, 0 – 100 vol% hydrogen. In the experiments with natural gas the MultiRae sensors are used. (0-100% LFL and 0-100 vol%).
- In addition, the natural gas or hydrogen concentration will be measured at 0.5 meters from the housing. The two sensors (all MultiRae's) are placed at 1 meter above ground level. These meters contain both a ppm sensor and a LFL sensor for hydrogen.

Adjusting the gas cabinet

In HyDelta 3.0, the question was formulated which simple adjustments (involving ventilation) can be made to improve the ventilation capabilities of an (existing) housing. After consultation with the EAG, it was decided to use the ½ m³ cabinet again that was also tested in previous HyDelta projects. This offers the advantage that this cabinet can be easily adjusted in terms of ventilation. In addition, experiments have already been carried out with this cabinet in its original state (without adjustments). This housing has a standard ventilation of 2% (top ventilation), which is related to the floor surface area.

Before starting the process of adjusting the cabinet, cabinet manufacturers were contacted to investigate to what extent they (already) receive this request from the market. Cabinets such as those used for gas distribution are also used in other sectors. Placing multiple grilles in the side panels of a housing is regularly done for pumps housings for water authorities and applications in electricity (such as fast chargers). In this case, ventilation is mainly used to remove heat produced by the equipment in the housing. These considerations have been included in this study.

By placing four elongated grilles in the cabinet for HyDelta testing, ventilation is increased from 2% to almost 14%. Two grilles are placed at the front, two at the back.

Wind and ventilation

The wind can have a major influence on the experiments. During HyDelta 1.0, two situations were therefore created, namely an indoor situation (windless situation) and an outdoor situation. In order to simulate a windless situation, the cabinet station is placed in a large tent. In addition, the same series of measurements are performed on a day that is expected to have a constant wind force (wind force 2 or 4) in order to limit the influence due to natural draught.

During HyDelta 2.0, it was decided to perform all experiments as much as possible in a windless situation using a large tent. To check whether there was actually a windless (and not necessarily windless) situation, an indicative wind meter was used during the measurements. This is an anemometer of the brand and type Skywatch OELE, with a minimum measuring range of 0.6 m/s.

During HyDelta 3.0 an identical approach was chosen as in HyDelta 2.0. All experiments were performed in a windless situation as much as possible.

Photos of the setups

The gas pressure regulation station was tested in an indoor/windless situation. In practice, stations are always outside. However, it is expected that natural ventilation during times that are windless/ nearly no wind will be less effective compared to natural ventilation through wind. To simulate windless and/or windless situations, the 1/2m³ cabinet was placed in a tent.

Figure 12. 1/2 m³ cabinet is low-wind situation

Figure 13. The contents of the 1/2 m³ cabinet

From a gas cylinder, natural gas (L-gas) and hydrogen were added in a controlled manner into the cabinet using a mass flow controller (MFC). This gas flows out in the middle of the cabinet from a leak opening with a surface area of 0.25 and 0.025 mm² respectively^{as} described above.

Additional information about the test setup can be found in Appendix II (measuring equipment).

Figure 14. Overview of the test setup

Figure 15. The nozzle for simulating the gas leakage

Figure 16. One of the MFCs for dosing the gas

Figure 17. The gas bottles for the gas supply

Figure 18. MultiRAE Lite IR Natural Gas Detector

Figure 19. Riken Keiki NP 1000 Hydrogen detector

Appendix II – Measuring equipment used

Table 3– Used measuring equipment details

Description	Manufacture and type	Kiwa no.
Natural gas detector	MultiRAE Lite IR	114033
Natural gas detector	MultiRAE Lite IR	114034
Natural gas detector	MultiRAE Lite IR	114036
Natural gas detector	MultiRAE Lite IR	114037
Natural gas detector	MultiRAE Lite IR	114038
Natural gas detector	MultiRAE Lite IR	114039
Natural gas detector	MultiRAE Lite IR	114040
Natural gas detector	MultiRAE Lite IR	114041
Natural gas detector	MultiRAE Lite IR	114043
Hydrogen detector	Riken Keiki NP 1000	-
MFC (natural gas / hydrogen)	Bronkhorst, type F-201CV-RAD-22-V	-
MFC (natural gas / hydrogen)	Bronkhorst, type F-203AV-M50-RBD-FF-V	-

Natural gas

- The Multirae have a measuring range of 0 - 100% LFL and 0-100 vol% natural gas).
- The four Multirae sensors used as a measuring point at a greater distance (0.5 m downwind) from the gas pressure regulation station have a measuring range of 0 - 100% LFL and 0-100 vol% natural gas.

Hydrogen

- The Riken Keiki sensors have a measuring range of 0 – 100 vol% hydrogen.
- The four Multirae sensors used as a measuring point at a greater distance (0.5 m downwind) from the gas pressure regulation station have a measuring range of 0-1000 ppm hydrogen. These specific Multirae sensors are also equipped with a 0 – 100% LFL sensor for hydrogen.

Appendix III – Leakage rates and measurement method

Leakage rates

During HyDelta 1.0 and 2.0 extensive discussions were held about leak openings and leak rates. In the HyDelta 2.0 report on ventilation [2], the selected areas of attention are shown with the help of a diagram. In these diagrams the pressure is plotted against the leak rate (flow, which visualizes the “operating window”). In this way, it is clear for both natural gas and hydrogen which operational area is covered for the assumed leakages.

Figure 20. Selected leakage rates HyDelta 1.0 versus HyDelta 2.0 for natural gas

Figure 21. Selected leakage rates HyDelta 1.0 versus HyDelta 2.0 for hydrogen

Because the interesting leak rates are located in this “window”, this result was used for the execution of HyDelta 3.0. Based on the presented data from the various studies in the area of methane emissions and the previously mentioned DVGW study [5], it can be concluded that the leaks found in gas pressure regulating stations in the field (of 40 l/h natural gas) approximately correspond to the smallest leak (0.025 mm²) at the lowest proposed pressure (1 barg).

This leak rate of 40 l/h is an important factor in this study and was used as a starting point for drawing up the test matrix. In effect, this also ensures that regular leakage as it occurs under normal operating conditions has been included in this test program (again).

For HyDelta 3.0, natural gas leaks were chosen between 40 l/h and 640 l/h. For hydrogen, leaks were chosen between 125 l/h and 2000 l/h. Most leaks are in the working area of the HyDelta 2.0 study.

Measurement method

In order to gain a good insight into how increasing ventilation affects the gas concentration in a housing, a modified measurement method was defined. It was chosen to work with a realistic operational leak flow rate as a starting point. The modified housing will first be tested with this.

Based on research commissioned by the Dutch standards committee, it was determined that an operational leak is equivalent to 40 l/h of natural gas [4]. This is an important starting point for all follow-up research. During HyDelta 2.0, it was also determined that a leak at the same pressure and leak size opening results in a leak flow rate of 125 l/h (where a leak rate of 40 l/h was established for natural gas).

A test will be started with a leak of 40 l/h natural gas (respectively 125 l/h hydrogen) where the gas concentration in and around the housing will be measured until it stabilizes. After that, the leak rate will be doubled and measured again until the measured gas concentrations stabilize. In total, the leak rate will be doubled four times for both natural gas and hydrogen. This results in the following test matrix.

Table 4 Leakage rates for natural gas and hydrogen.

	Leak rate 1	Leak rate 2	Leak rate 3	Leak rate 4	Leak rate 5
Natural gas (m³_n/h) *	0.04	0.08	0.16	0.32	0.64
Natural gas (l/h) *	40	80	160	320	640
Natural gas (g/s) *	0.009	0.019	0.037	0.074	0.148
Hydrogen (m³_n/h) *	0.125	0.250	0.500	1.0	2.0
Hydrogen (l/h) *	125	250	500	1000	2000
Hydrogen (g/s) *	0.003	0.006	0.012	0.25	0.50

*) Rounding of numbers and significant figures reserved

The role of improved ventilation has been tested using the above matrix, in which maximum ventilation (top and bottom ventilation), top ventilation and cross ventilation have been tested. In all cases, the standard ventilation of 2% was maintained as originally designed.

In view of the practical feasibility of setting the leakage rate using an MFC, rounding and significant figures in these tables are reserved.

Processing measurements

In order to minimize the role of external factors, it was decided to report the bar charts with average values. These values are a representation of the instantaneous measurements over a period of time between 1 minute and 10 minutes. Error bars were used in the bar charts to provide insight into the minimum and maximum measured concentrations. The length of the error bar indicates the bandwidth of the measured concentrations during the experiment per measuring point. With this spread, the reader can see the effect of external influences (such as wind/natural draught). In this way, measurements can be compared with each other at a glance.

Appendix IV – Measurement results for natural gas and hydrogen

		VLL	VLR	ALL	ALR	VHL	VHR	AHL	AHR
		Voor-laag-links							
		Voor-laag-rechts							
		Achter-laag-links							
		Achter-laag-rechts							
		Voor-hoog-links							
		Voor-hoog-rechts							
		Achter-hoog-links							
		Achter-hoog-rechts							

x kortste afstand nozzle tot ingang sample sensor [mm]													
		in kast midden (gas uit)		Kant Hoog Ventilator		Voor Laag Links		Voor Laag Rechts		Achter Laag rechts		Achter Hoog Links	
x [mm]		KL	KM	KH	KHV	VLL	VLR	ALL	ALR	VHL	VHR	AHL	AHR
		325	193	705	790	346	324	467	389	704	684	736	726

Natural gas measurement results – maximum ventilation, top ventilation and cross ventilation

Aardgas													
Max ventilatie													
	KL	KM	KH	KHV	VLL	VLR	ALL	ALR	VHL	VHR	AHL	AHR	Average
max 0.64 m ³ /h	1.0%	3.4%	1.5%	3.4%	1.4%	1.1%	1.0%	0.7%	3.3%	3.2%	3.6%	3.5%	2.3%
min 0.64 m ³ /h	0.4%	2.9%	1.0%	2.1%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.7%	2.4%	2.2%	0.4%	1.1%
max 0.32 m ³ /h	0.5%	2.4%	0.6%	1.7%	1.1%	0.7%	1.0%	0.6%	2.8%	2.0%	2.5%	1.6%	1.5%
min 0.32 m ³ /h	0.2%	2.1%	0.2%	1.2%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.5%	0.7%	1.6%	0.4%	0.7%
max 0.16 m ³ /h	0.4%	2.8%	0.6%	0.9%	0.4%	0.3%	0.6%	0.1%	2.3%	1.1%	2.5%	0.9%	1.1%
min 0.16 m ³ /h	0.2%	2.5%	0.1%	0.9%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.4%	0.7%	0.5%	0.4%	0.4%
max 0.08 m ³ /h	0.1%	2.4%	0.1%	0.6%	0.0%	0.1%	0.4%	0.0%	0.6%	0.4%	1.8%	1.0%	0.6%
min 0.08 m ³ /h	0.1%	2.2%	0.0%	0.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.2%	0.2%	0.5%	0.3%	0.3%
max 0.04 m ³ /h	0.2%	2.7%	0.1%	0.3%	0.2%	0.1%	0.3%	0.1%	0.2%	0.2%	0.2%	0.4%	0.4%
min 0.04 m ³ /h	0.1%	2.2%	0.0%	0.1%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.1%	0.2%

Aardgas													
Bovenventilatie													
	KL	KM	KH	KHV	VLL	VLR	ALL	ALR	VHL	VHR	AHL	AHR	Average
max 0.64 m ³ /h	1.1%	6.2%	3.4%	5.8%	4.4%	5.4%	4.9%	5.5%	4.0%	3.2%	4.7%	3.1%	4.3%
min 0.64 m ³ /h	0.0%	5.6%	2.0%	4.6%	1.9%	2.8%	2.6%	3.2%	2.6%	1.9%	4.0%	1.5%	2.7%
max 0.32 m ³ /h	0.3%	3.4%	1.5%	3.2%	3.7%	1.9%	4.2%	2.9%	3.5%	1.0%	3.3%	3.6%	2.7%
min 0.32 m ³ /h	0.1%	2.8%	0.9%	2.4%	1.9%	0.4%	1.9%	0.7%	0.7%	0.1%	1.0%	0.5%	1.1%
max 0.16 m ³ /h	0.2%	2.1%	1.5%	1.9%	2.9%	1.3%	3.6%	2.2%	0.4%	0.2%	1.7%	1.9%	1.7%
min 0.16 m ³ /h	0.1%	1.4%	0.1%	0.9%	0.8%	0.5%	0.5%	0.8%	0.1%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.5%
max 0.08 m ³ /h	0.3%	1.4%	0.2%	1.0%	1.8%	0.6%	1.0%	1.0%	0.2%	0.3%	0.5%	0.2%	0.7%
min 0.08 m ³ /h	0.2%	1.3%	0.1%	0.7%	0.6%	0.2%	0.1%	0.3%	0.2%	0.1%	0.3%	0.0%	0.3%
max 0.04 m ³ /h	0.3%	1.1%	0.1%	0.5%	0.9%	0.4%	1.4%	0.5%	0.2%	0.1%	0.4%	0.1%	0.5%
min 0.04 m ³ /h	0.1%	0.9%	0.0%	0.3%	0.1%	0.1%	0.4%	0.2%	0.1%	0.0%	0.2%	0.0%	0.2%

Aardgas													
Kruisventilatie													
	KL	KM	KH	KHV	VLL	VLR	ALL	ALR	VHL	VHR	AHL	AHR	Average
max 0.64 m ³ /h	1.0%	5.5%	3.4%	5.1%	5.0%	5.1%	4.8%	5.2%	1.8%	3.4%	3.9%	0.7%	3.7%
min 0.64 m ³ /h	0.4%	5.3%	2.9%	4.0%	2.5%	4.2%	2.2%	3.4%	0.2%	1.9%	3.5%	0.0%	2.5%
max 0.32 m ³ /h	0.8%	3.2%	1.8%	3.1%	3.5%	3.1%	3.1%	3.3%	2.9%	1.2%	4.0%	1.6%	2.6%
min 0.32 m ³ /h	0.2%	2.0%	0.8%	1.8%	2.1%	1.8%	1.7%	1.3%	0.1%	0.1%	1.6%	0.0%	1.1%
max 0.16 m ³ /h	0.6%	1.6%	0.6%	1.4%	2.7%	1.4%	2.8%	1.6%	0.6%	0.6%	1.5%	0.4%	1.3%
min 0.16 m ³ /h	0.2%	1.3%	0.3%	1.0%	1.1%	0.6%	1.4%	0.6%	0.1%	0.2%	0.7%	0.0%	0.6%
max 0.08 m ³ /h	0.4%	1.4%	0.2%	0.9%	1.5%	0.9%	1.3%	0.9%	0.2%	0.4%	0.7%	0.4%	0.8%
min 0.08 m ³ /h	0.3%	1.0%	0.1%	0.5%	0.6%	0.4%	0.6%	0.4%	0.1%	0.2%	0.4%	0.0%	0.4%
max 0.04 m ³ /h	0.1%	1.1%	0.0%	0.3%	0.2%	0.4%	0.2%	0.4%	0.2%	0.1%	0.3%	0.1%	0.3%
min 0.04 m ³ /h	0.1%	0.9%	0.0%	0.2%	0.1%	0.1%	0.1%	0.2%	0.1%	0.1%	0.2%	0.0%	0.2%

Hydrogen measurement results – maximum ventilation, top ventilation and cross ventilation

Hoog-links (VHL/ AHL)

Laag-links (VLL/ ALL)

Laag-rechts (VLR/ ALR)

VLL	Voor-laag-links
VLR	Voor-laag-rechts
ALL	Achter-laag-links
ALR	Achter-laag-rechts
VHL	Voor-hoog-links
VHR	Voor-hoog-rechts
AHL	Achter-hoog-links
AHR	Achter-hoog-rechts

x		kortste afstand nozzle tot ingang sample sensor [mm]																				
		in kast midden (geen wij)		kast Hoog Ventilatie		Voor Laag Links		Voor Laag Rechts		Achter Laag links		Achter Laag rechts		Voor Hoog Links		Voor Hoog Rechts		Achter Hoog Links		Achter Hoog Rechts		
x [mm]		KL	KM	KH	KHV	VLL	VLR	ALL	ALR	VHL	VHR	AHL	AHR	VLL	VLR	ALL	ALR	VHL	VHR	AHL	AHR	
325		193	705	760	346	324	407	389	704	694	736	726										

Waterstof Max ventilatie													
	KL	KM	KH	KHV	VLL	VLR	ALL	ALR	VHL	VHR	AHL	AHR	Average
max 2.100 m ³ /h	0,0%	7,0%	6,5%	6,3%					6,2%	6,4%	6,0%	6,0%	5,7%
min 2.100 m ³ /h	0,0%	7,4%	6,3%	5,8%					3,6%	4,2%	3,4%	3,0%	4,2%
max 1.000 m ³ /h	0,0%	6,8%	4,6%	4,4%					4,0%	4,3%	4,1%	4,0%	4,0%
min 1.000 m ³ /h	0,0%	5,8%	4,0%	3,6%					2,5%	3,6%	0,5%	0,0%	2,5%
max 0.500 m ³ /h	0,0%	6,0%	3,1%	2,8%					2,5%	2,6%	1,9%	2,6%	2,6%
min 0.500 m ³ /h	0,0%	6,0%	1,9%	2,1%					0,6%	0,6%	1,3%	0,3%	1,6%
max 0.250 m ³ /h	0,0%	7,0%	2,2%	1,9%					1,6%	1,7%	1,2%	1,1%	2,1%
min 0.250 m ³ /h	0,0%	5,9%	1,2%	0,6%					0,2%	0,0%	0,1%	0,1%	1,0%
max 0.125 m ³ /h	0,0%	7,1%	1,4%	1,1%					0,4%	0,5%	0,7%	0,9%	1,5%
min 0.125 m ³ /h	0,0%	5,9%	0,0%	0,2%					0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,8%

Waterstof Bovenventilatie													
	KL	KM	KH	KHV	VLL	VLR	ALL	ALR	VHL	VHR	AHL	AHR	Average
max 2.100 m ³ /h	0,0%	9,1%	9,4%	9,1%	0,2%	0,6%	0,8%	0,8%	5,5%	8,1%	8,3%	9,4%	5,1%
min 2.100 m ³ /h	0,0%	8,3%	8,6%	8,2%	0,0%	0,2%	0,2%	1,2%	2,4%	1,9%	7,0%	3,2%	3,2%
max 1.000 m ³ /h	0,0%	5,7%	6,5%	6,5%	0,1%	0,6%	0,6%	0,2%	5,2%	6,5%	3,8%	6,3%	3,5%
min 1.000 m ³ /h	0,0%	5,1%	3,4%	4,6%	0,0%	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	2,7%	2,1%	0,4%	4,2%	1,9%
max 0.500 m ³ /h	0,0%	4,3%	4,9%	4,4%	0,0%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%	3,0%	4,3%	3,7%	4,7%	2,5%
min 0.500 m ³ /h	0,0%	3,7%	2,8%	2,5%	0,0%	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	1,0%	0,6%	0,5%	2,7%	1,2%
max 0.250 m ³ /h	0,0%	3,0%	3,2%	2,6%	0,1%	0,2%	0,1%	0,1%	2,3%	2,7%	1,9%	2,2%	1,5%
min 0.250 m ³ /h	0,0%	2,0%	2,8%	2,1%	0,0%	0,1%	0,0%	0,1%	1,0%	0,9%	0,5%	0,9%	0,9%
max 0.125 m ³ /h	0,0%	3,7%	4,9%	1,5%	0,2%	0,4%	0,3%	0,3%	1,1%	1,0%	1,4%	1,4%	1,1%
min 0.125 m ³ /h	0,0%	2,8%	1,0%	0,8%	0,0%	0,2%	0,2%	0,1%	0,0%	0,2%	0,0%	0,4%	0,5%

Waterstof kruisventilatie													
	KL	KM	KH	KHV	VLL	VLR	ALL	ALR	VHL	VHR	AHL	AHR	Average
max 2.100 m ³ /h	0,0%	9,9%	8,1%	7,8%	0,2%	1,2%	0,1%	0,0%	8,0%	8,1%	7,9%	7,9%	4,9%
min 2.100 m ³ /h	0,0%	8,9%	7,7%	7,2%	0,0%	0,4%	0,0%	0,0%	6,0%	5,3%	7,5%	7,6%	4,2%
max 1.000 m ³ /h	0,0%	6,8%	5,5%	5,1%	0,5%	0,5%	0,0%	0,0%	5,5%	5,4%	5,3%	5,5%	3,3%
min 1.000 m ³ /h	0,0%	5,9%	4,9%	4,6%	0,0%	0,2%	0,0%	0,0%	2,2%	1,7%	5,0%	5,1%	2,5%
max 0.500 m ³ /h	0,0%	4,1%	3,9%	3,4%	0,3%	0,4%	0,2%	0,4%	3,2%	3,8%	3,6%	3,8%	2,3%
min 0.500 m ³ /h	0,0%	3,3%	1,8%	2,4%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	1,0%	0,5%	2,5%	3,0%	1,2%
max 0.250 m ³ /h	0,0%	3,0%	2,8%	2,5%	0,0%	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	2,3%	2,6%	2,6%	2,7%	1,6%
min 0.250 m ³ /h	0,0%	2,6%	1,6%	1,3%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,4%	0,3%	2,2%	1,4%	0,8%
max 0.125 m ³ /h	0,0%	4,2%	1,9%	1,6%	0,0%	0,1%	0,0%	0,0%	1,2%	1,3%	1,5%	1,7%	1,1%
min 0.125 m ³ /h	0,0%	3,3%	0,5%	0,9%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,5%	1,2%	1,1%	0,6%

Waterstof concentratieverdeling voor verschillende lekdebieten: maximale ventilatie (0.5m3 kast)

Waterstof concentratieverdeling voor verschillende lekdebieten: bovenventilatie (0.5m3 kast)

Waterstof concentratieverdeling voor verschillende lekdebieten: kruisventilatie (0.5m3 kast)

